

Selecting Locations and Sizes of Battery Storage Systems Based on the Frequency of the Center-of-Inertia and Principle Component Analysis

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Abstract—This paper develops, implements, and tests a method for selecting the locations and sizes of battery storage systems for power systems with distributed power generation. The developed method is based on calculating the coherency index for each bus to determine its contribution to the frequency of the center-of-inertia (COI) during and post a transient event. Once the coherency index is calculated for all buses, the principle component analysis (PCA) is used to identify the buses with consistent low values of the coherency index. These buses are considered as candidate locations for battery storage systems. In addition, the lowest values of the coherency index are used to determine the required sizes of battery storage systems to be connected at the buses with low contributions to the frequency of the COI. The performance of the principle component analysis with center-of-inertia (PCA-COI) method is evaluated for the Barbados power system for various transient events. Performance results show that battery storage systems (selected using the proposed method) can effectively improve the frequency stability with minor sensitivity to the levels of distributed power generation, loading levels, and/or type or location of transient events.

Index Terms—Battery storage systems, principle component analysis, power system transients, and power system frequency stability.

I. INTRODUCTION

Many power systems have made structural and operational changes as part of implementing the de-regulated operation. The de-regulated operation of any power system offers several advantages, including energy saving programs (demand response), optimized power system functions (load-side control), high levels of sustainable energy production (generation mixes), and improved system stability and reliability (distributed generation units (DGUs) and energy storage systems (ESSs)) [1]–[11]. The integration of energy storage systems (ESSs) has been identified as an effective approach to improve frequency and voltage stability, power quality, and overall efficiency [10]–[12]. In addition, ESSs are widely used to mitigate the continuous changes in the power delivered by distributed generation units (DGUs) (e.g. wind and solar energy systems) [1]–[8]. For power system applications, several types of ESSs are commercially available with different ratings, power densities, response times, etc. (see reference [4] for details). Battery storage systems (BSSs) have demonstrated several advantages over other ESSs, including modularity, response times, charge/discharge cycles, cost, and life span [4]–[7].

The codes and practices of power systems recommend operating ESSs with short response times (supercapacitors, battery banks, superconducting magnetic energy storage (SMES)) to mitigate fast variations in the power delivered by DGUs, improve the frequency and voltage stability, and improve power quality.

Power systems codes practices also recommend operating ESSs with long response times (pumped hydro and flywheels) to mitigate small and slow frequency variations. These practices are set considering the following aspects of ESSs [9]–[15]:

- The type and cost (capital and running);
- The size and location;
- The control and operation.

The latest advancements in the battery technology and power electronics converters have facilitated manufacturing BSSs with high power ratings at feasible costs. As a result, many power systems have expressed interests in deploying high power rated BSSs. However, power system interests in BSSs have faced challenges that are centered by the selection of sizes and locations of BSSs. In order to overcome such challenges, several research works have been carried out to develop methods and procedures for selecting the sizes and locations of BSSs in power systems. The early research works to address these challenges have been based selecting the locations for BSSs to achieve a composite reliability index of the distribution system. These research works have concluded that properly located BSSs can improve the reliability of distribution systems. Nonetheless, these conclusions have been drawn without considering the power ratings of BSSs, which can be critical as the number of BSSs is increased [1], [8]–[12]. Other research works have employed the reliability indexes to specify the power ratings (sizes) of BSSs to be deployed in distribution systems. However, these research works have not considered BSS locations when selecting BSS sizes [1], [9]–[15].

A systematic procedure has been developed to select the power ratings of BSSs as backup power supplies for critical loads. This procedure has been developed to meet reliability indexes without considering models for distribution systems. The concern for employing this procedure has been raised as possible impacts of BSS locations can not fully analyzed [1], [13]–[15]. Another approach based on the operation of BSSs has been introduced to specify BSS sizes for distribution systems. This approach has been implemented by connecting an individual BSS to an infinite bus that includes a model for the distribution system [1], [9], [16], [17]. This lumped network approach has an advantage of determining BSS sizes with minor dependence on the distribution network model. Nevertheless, the lumped network approach has a disadvantage due to its inability to provide locations for BSSs [9], [15], [18]. This approach has been improved by incorporating an explicit model of the distribution system, where each node has a BSS with an initial size [19]. Despite this improvement, the lumped network approach has been validated for distribution

systems that are supplied by conventional generating units only [1], [9]–[19].

The review of existing approaches to select locations and sizes of BSSs (for power systems) reveals the following:

- i) developed to meet distribution system reliability;
- ii) developed without relationships between locations and sizes of BSSs;
- iii) developed and tested for distribution systems only;
- iv) developed to select either BSS locations or BSS sizes.

The objective of this paper is to develop and test a new approach to select locations and sizes of BSSs for power systems with renewable energy sources. The proposed approach is to consider the entire power system with the system frequency as the main constraint. This objective is achieved by determining the contribution of each bus to the frequency of the equivalent center-of-inertia (COI) using the coherency index. Furthermore, this paper employs the principal component analysis (PCA) to identify the buses with consistent low coherency indexes. Such buses are considered candidate locations for BSSs. The lowest values of coherency indexes for each candidate location are used to select the size of the BSS to be connected at that bus. The PCA-COI approach is implemented and tested for the Barbados power system, which has conventional generating units and solar energy systems. Test results demonstrate improved stability and operation of the Barbados power system with BSSs located and sized using the proposed PCA-COI approach.

II. BUS COHERENCY AND COHERENCY INDEX IN POWER SYSTEMS

A. Overview of Bus Coherency

Power systems can experience various types of transient events that can initiate system-wide frequency oscillations. In such conditions, a power system's behavior is driven by the responses of generating units, which can be grouped based on their coherency [1], [19]. The concept of generator coherency has been adapted as an effective tool for modeling and analyzing power system behavior during and post transient events [1], [19]–[24]. Several methods for determining the generator coherency have been developed, among which are the fast Fourier transform, artificial neural networks, Hilbert transform, particle swarm optimization, nonlinear Koopman modes, support vector clustering, and principal component analysis (PCA) [1], [19]–[25].

Generator coherency methods start by defining the angular speed of the equivalent center-of-inertia (COI), Ω^{COI} , as [25]:

$$\Omega^{\text{COI}} = \frac{1}{\mathcal{H}} \sum_{n=1}^N H_n \Omega_n; \quad n, N \in \mathbb{Z} \quad (1)$$

where Ω_n is the angular speed of generator n , H_n is the inertia constant of generator n in seconds, and \mathcal{H} is given as:

$$\mathcal{H} = \sum_{n=1}^N H_n$$

Using equation (1), the frequency of COI, f^{COI} , is stated as [25]:

$$f^{\text{COI}} = \frac{\Omega^{\text{COI}}}{2\pi} = \frac{1}{\mathcal{H}} \sum_{n=1}^N H_n f_n \quad (2)$$

where f_n is the frequency at the terminals of generator n . The determination of f^{COI} allows stating a vector for frequency deviations ($\Delta \mathbf{f}$) at bus k (a generator bus or a load bus) with respect to the COI. The vector $\Delta \mathbf{f}$ is defined over a time interval $[t_1, t_2]$, where t_1 is the starting time of a transient event, and t_2 is the time a steady-state condition is regained. The vector $\Delta \mathbf{f}$ for bus k is defined as [19]:

$$\Delta \mathbf{f}_k = [\Delta f_k|_{(t_1+\Delta t)}, \Delta f_k|_{(t_1+2\Delta t)}, \dots, \Delta f_k|_{(t_2)}] \quad (3)$$

where $M \in \mathbb{Z}$, Δt is the sampling time, and Δf_k is given as:

$$\Delta f_k|_{(t_1+m\Delta t)} = f^{\text{COI}}|_{(t_1+m\Delta t)} - f_k|_{(t_1+m\Delta t)}; \quad m = 1, \dots, M$$

Since any power system may experience various transient events, f^{COI} may deviate from the nominal frequency, f_o , during and post transient events. As a result, a vector of frequency deviations can be defined for the COI as:

$$\Delta \mathbf{f}_{\text{COI}} = [\Delta f_{\text{COI}}|_{(t_1+\Delta t)}, \Delta f_{\text{COI}}|_{(t_1+2\Delta t)}, \dots, \Delta f_{\text{COI}}|_{(t_2)}] \quad (4)$$

where each Δf_{COI} is determined as:

$$\Delta f_{\text{COI}}|_{(t_1+m\Delta t)} = f_o - f^{\text{COI}}|_{(t_1+m\Delta t)}; \quad m = 1, \dots, M$$

Frequency deviation vectors for the COI and other buses, can be used to evaluate the coherency of bus k with the COI. The coherency of bus k with the COI is quantified by the coherency index \mathcal{C} , which is defined for bus k as [1], [19]–[21]:

$$\mathcal{C}_k = \frac{\Delta \mathbf{f}_k \times [\Delta \mathbf{f}_{\text{COI}}]^T}{\|\Delta \mathbf{f}_k\| \times \|\Delta \mathbf{f}_{\text{COI}}\|} \quad (5)$$

where $\|\cdot\|$ is the Euclidean norm. The value of \mathcal{C}_k ranges as:

$$-1 \leq \mathcal{C}_k \leq 1, \quad \text{with } \mathcal{C}_k \in \mathbb{R}$$

For $\mathcal{C}_k = 1$, bus k is coherent with the COI and has a full contribution to f^{COI} . Similarly, for $\mathcal{C}_k = -1$, bus k is incoherent with the COI and has no contribution to f^{COI} (see equation (8) in reference [20]). It should be noted that in a steady-state condition, \mathcal{C} (for any bus) has an indeterminate value due to $f^{\text{COI}} \cong f_o$ causing $\|\Delta \mathbf{f}_{\text{COI}}\| \cong 0$.

B. Determining the Coherency Index \mathcal{C}

The value of \mathcal{C}_k (calculated using equation (5)) for any transient event, quantifies the contribution of bus k to f^{COI} for that transient event. Buses with low contributions to f^{COI} have low inertia constants, thus experiencing dynamic changes in their power injection [1], [5], [20]–[25]. The identification of such buses requires determining their \mathcal{C} , which mandates the vectors of frequency deviations as in equations (3) and (4). The desired vectors of frequency deviations for all buses in a power system can be determined as:

- i) $\Delta \mathbf{f}_{\text{COI}}$: The inertia constant and instantaneous values of the frequency of each generating unit are required as inputs to

equation (2) to calculate f^{COI} at each Δt . The calculated value of f^{COI} at each Δt together with f_o are used as inputs to equation (4). It should be noted that the frequency of each generating unit can be directly measured (required by the governor control). Finally, generating units connected to a bus are expected to have the same coherency index as they have the same frequency [1], [19]–[22].

- ii) Δf_k : The values of f^{COI} and f_k at each Δt are required as inputs to equation (4). The calculated values of Δf_k at each Δt are used as inputs to equation (3). The value of f_k at each Δt can be obtained by a direct measurement using a phasor measurement unit (PMU), or it can be calculated using the rate of change in the voltage angle θ_k as [1], [20]:

$$f_k|_{(t+\Delta t)} = \frac{1}{2\pi f_o} \left(\frac{\theta_k|_{(t+\Delta t)} - \theta_k|_{(t)}}{\Delta t} \right) \quad (6)$$

Vectors of frequency deviations are used to calculate \mathcal{C} using equation (5), which implies that \mathcal{C} (for any bus) may have different values for different transient events. This nature of \mathcal{C} reflects the diverse behaviors of a power system during and post transient events [1], [20]–[23]. On one hand, the employment of the coherency index (to create groups of coherent buses) is based on selecting the worst transient event [1], [19]–[25]. On the other hand, \mathcal{C} can quantify the required contribution of each bus to restore the COI frequency post a transient event. Such features of \mathcal{C} can be advantageous in:

- enhancing responses of generator controllers;
- providing limits for load-side control actions;
- identifying load buses with low contributions to f^{COI} ;
- controlling the power injected by or stored in BSSs.

The focus of this paper is on (c), and the employment of \mathcal{C} to select locations and sizes of BSSs in a power system.

III. PROCESSING COHERENCY INDEXES USING THE PRINCIPLE COMPONENT ANALYSIS

The previous section has discussed the coherency index \mathcal{C} , and its nature of having different values due to different transient events. The \mathcal{C} can be employed in selecting locations and sizes of ESSs, as it quantifies the coherency of any bus with the COI during and post transient events. As \mathcal{C} has different values for different transient events, its effective employment requires processing its values determined for different transient events. Such a processing aims to obtain the patterns and boundary values for \mathcal{C} at each bus. There are various methods to obtain such patterns and boundary values of \mathcal{C} , among which is the principle component analysis.

A. The Principle Component Analysis

The principal component analysis (PCA) is an orthogonal-rotation that transforms a set of correlated variables to another set of uncorrelated variables. The set of uncorrelated variables obtained by the PCA is called *principal components*, which are a linear combination of the original correlated variables. These principal components are derived in a descending order of importance, where the first principal component accounts for

the largest possible variation in the original correlated variables [25], [26]. The PCA has been found advantageous for eliminating redundant information, reducing the number of dimensions, and identifying patterns in high dimension data sets [26].

A data set $\mathbf{D}[M \times \ell]$, with ℓ vectors of M elements, can be constructed by measurements over a time interval $[t_1, t_2]$ (M sampling instants). For such a set, the PCA reconstructs \mathbf{D} using a set of ℓ orthonormal basis functions $\{\varphi_l\}_{l=1}^{\ell}$, which are created by the eigenvalues and eigenvectors of the covariance matrix determined for \mathbf{D} . The orthonormal basis functions can be defined as [25], [26]:

$$\mathcal{C}\varphi_l = \mu_l\varphi_l \quad (7)$$

where \mathcal{C} is the covariance matrix of \mathbf{D} and μ_l is the eigenvalue corresponding to the eigenvector φ_l of \mathcal{C} . It should be noted that each column in \mathbf{D} has to be processed as:

$$D_{lm}^u = \sigma_l \left(D_{lm} - \widehat{D}_l \right); \quad m = 1, 2, \dots, M \quad (8)$$

where σ_l is the standard deviation of the data in column l in \mathbf{D} , and \widehat{D}_l is mean value of the data in column l in \mathbf{D} . Once all columns of \mathbf{D} are processed, the PCA can be stated as [25]:

$$\mathbf{P} = \mathbf{D}^u \times \Phi \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{D}^u is the processed version of \mathbf{D} (using equation (8)), and Φ is the matrix of the orthonormal basis functions as:

$$\Phi = [\varphi_1, \varphi_2, \dots, \varphi_\ell]^T \quad (10)$$

The application of the PCA on a data set implies that the component obtained using φ_l (corresponding to the largest eigenvalue) will contain more information than other components. As a result, a possible reduction in the data dimension can be made by neglecting components related to basis functions with small eigenvalues [25], [26]. The elimination of such PCA components facilitates forming clusters, which can identify patterns in the original data \mathbf{D} .

B. Principal Component Analysis of Coherency Indexes

The coherency index \mathcal{C} can be determined for all buses in a power system for different transient events (e.g. faults, load rejections, changes in load power demands, loss of generating units, etc.). Determined values of \mathcal{C} (for all buses) due to transient events $b = 1, 2, \dots, B$ can be viewed as a data set that is formed for an N -bus power system as:

$$\mathcal{C} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathcal{C}_{11} & \mathcal{C}_{21} & \dots & \mathcal{C}_{N1} \\ \mathcal{C}_{12} & \mathcal{C}_{22} & \dots & \mathcal{C}_{N2} \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathcal{C}_{1B} & \mathcal{C}_{2B} & \dots & \mathcal{C}_{NB} \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

where \mathcal{C}_{nb} is the coherence index of bus n ($n = 1, 2, \dots, N$) due to the transient event b ($b = 1, 2, \dots, B$).

The matrix \mathcal{C} , determined for B transient events will have diverse elements that demonstrate the coherency of different buses with the COI. Buses with a low coherency with the COI can be identified by performing the PCA on the matrix \mathcal{C} . Prior to the PCA of \mathcal{C} , columns of \mathcal{C} have to be processed using equation

(8). The value of $C_{nb}(t_o)$ quantifies the contribution of bus n to the COI at time t_o during or post the transient event b . The ideal $C_{nb}(t_o)$ is the one obtained for:

$$f_n(t_o) = f^{\text{COI}}(t_o) : \text{ for all } t_o \quad (12)$$

During a steady-state condition, the frequency at any power system bus can be related to the active power injected at that bus as [27], [28]:

a) For a generator:

$$f_g = (1 - \kappa\xi_g) f_o - \kappa P_g \quad (13)$$

where κ is the droop characteristic constant of the generator, ξ_g is the frequency damping factor of the generator, and P_g is the active power produced by the generator.

b) For a load:

$$f_k = f_o - \frac{\Delta P_k}{\xi P_{ko}} \quad (14)$$

where ΔP_k is the change in active power delivered to the load, ξ is the frequency damping factor of the load, and P_{ko} is the rated active power of the load.

Equations (13) and (14) highlight the dependence of the frequency at any bus on the active power injected at that bus. These equations also indicate that accurate and fast regulation of the active power injected at bus n can minimize the frequency deviations at that bus, thus satisfying the condition in equation (12) [1], [19], [20], [28]. On one hand, the droop control of generating units can provide effective and accurate regulation of the active power produced by these units. On the other hand, accurate and fast regulation of the active power delivered to load buses can be achieved by a proper selection of BSSs connected at these buses [1]–[5].

IV. SELECTING THE LOCATIONS AND SIZES OF BSSs USING THE PCA-COI METHOD

The relationships between the power injected at any bus and frequency deviations provide an approach to correct low coherency indexes (minimize frequency deviations) using BSSs. In order to implement this approach, buses with low coherency indexes have to be identified. In addition, low values of coherency indexes can provide an accurate tool for selecting the required power ratings (size) for each BSS to be connected at buses with low coherency indexes. The first step to implement the PCA-COI method is to apply the PCA on the matrix of coherency indexes, which are determined for all buses due to various transient events.

A. Implementing the PCA-COI Method

The implementation of the PCA-COI method involves determining frequency deviations for all buses and COI due to various transient events. Determined frequency deviations are used to calculate the coherency index for each bus due to each selected transient event. Once all coherency indexes are calculated (\mathcal{C} is constructed), the PCA can be applied on \mathcal{C} to identify buses with consistent low coherency indexes. The following steps summarize the implementation of the proposed PCA-COI method.

- 1- Select transient events ($b = 1, 2, \dots, B$) that can create large frequency variations in the power system at hand. Such events can be faults, step changes in load power demands, loss of transmission lines, loss of generating units, load rejection, and dynamic changes in distributed power generation.
- 2- Determine $\Delta \mathbf{f}_{\text{COI}}$, $\Delta \mathbf{f}$ and \mathcal{C} , for each bus due to each transient event.
- 3- Construct the matrix \mathcal{C} for all selected transient events, and process its columns using equation (8) to obtain \mathcal{C}^u .
- 4- Apply the PCA on \mathcal{C}^u , obtain the matrix \mathbf{P} , and identify buses with low principal components.
- 5- Select the lowest value of \mathcal{C} for each identified bus.

The steps to implement the PCA-COI method ensure identifying the buses that have low contributions to the COI frequency during and post transient events. These identified buses are candidate locations for BSSs to support the frequency stability. It should be noted that the lowest value of \mathcal{C} , for each identified bus, can be due to a different transient event.

B. Sizing BSSs Using the PCA-COI Method

In order to utilize the PCA-COI method in estimating the required active power to increase the contribution of bus n to the COI frequency, changes in the active power at bus n have to be related to C_n . Such a relationship can be created based on equation (14). At load bus n , the frequency deviation Δf_n is [1]:

$$\Delta f_n = f^{\text{COI}} - f_n \implies f_n = f^{\text{COI}} - \Delta f_n \quad (15)$$

Substituting f_n from equation (14) into equation (15) yields:

$$f^{\text{COI}} - \Delta f_n = f_o - \frac{\Delta P_n}{\xi P_{no}} \quad (16)$$

Rearranging equation (16) produces:

$$\Delta P_n = \xi P_{no} (f_o - f^{\text{COI}} + \Delta f_n) \quad (17)$$

The statement of equation (15) simplifies equation (17) to:

$$\Delta P_n = \xi P_{no} (\Delta f_{\text{COI}} + \Delta f_n) \quad (18)$$

Equation (18) can be evaluated using values of Δf_{COI} and Δf_n determined and measured at different time instants, that is:

$$\Delta \mathbf{P}_n = \xi P_{no} (\Delta \mathbf{f}_{\text{COI}} + \Delta \mathbf{f}_n) \quad (19)$$

where $\Delta \mathbf{P}_n$ is the vector of changes in the active power injected at bus n during the time interval $[t_1, t_2]$ as:

$$\Delta \mathbf{P}_n = [\Delta P_n|_{(t_1+\Delta t)}, \Delta P_n|_{(t_1+2\Delta t)}, \dots, \Delta P_n|_{(t_2)}] \quad (20)$$

Equation (19) can be rearranged and stated using vectors as:

$$\Delta \mathbf{f}_n = \frac{\Delta \mathbf{P}_n}{\xi P_{no}} - \Delta \mathbf{f}_{\text{COI}} \quad (21)$$

Substituting equation (21) into equation (5), and rearranging the expression for C_n yield:

$$\frac{\Delta \mathbf{P}_n \times [\Delta \mathbf{f}_{\text{COI}}]^T}{\xi P_{no}} = \alpha C_n + \Delta \mathbf{f}_{\text{COI}} \times [\Delta \mathbf{f}_{\text{COI}}]^T \quad (22)$$

Fig. 1. A flowchart to implement the PCA-COI method for an N -bus power system with B transient events, and to determine the locations and sizes of BSSs.

where $\alpha = \|\Delta \mathbf{f}_k\| \times \|\Delta \mathbf{f}_{COI}\|$.

Remarks For Equation (22)

- Instantaneous changes in the active power at a load bus can be related to the coherency index of that bus.
- Adequate regulation of the active power injected at a load bus, during and post a transient event can result in $\Delta \mathbf{P} \rightarrow 0$, thus $\Delta \mathbf{f} \rightarrow \Delta \mathbf{f}_{COI}$.
- Equation (22) provides a basis for estimating the inertia constant of bus n (see Ref. [30]).

The required active power from a BSS, connected to load bus n , can be estimated using the value of $\Delta P_n|_{t=t_2}$. The value of $\Delta P_n|_{t=t_2}$ is selected to ensure regulating the active power injected at load bus n , thus reaching a steady-state condition post a transient event. The value of $\Delta P_n|_{t=t_2}$ can be expressed as:

$$\Delta P_n|_{t=t_2} = \xi P_{no} \left(\frac{\alpha C_n}{\Delta f_{COI}|_{t=t_2}} + \Delta f_{COI}|_{t=t_2} \right) \quad (23)$$

Equation (23) leads to stating the estimated power ratings (size) of a BSS at load bus n as:

$$(P_{ESS})_n = \Delta P_n|_{t=t_2} \quad (24)$$

where $(P_{ESS})_n$ is the power ratings of the BSS to be connected to bus n . In order to select the required size of a BSS at bus n , $(P_{ESS})_n$ is calculated using the lowest value of C_n as:

$$(P_{ESS})_{no} = \xi P_{no} \left(\frac{\alpha C_{nw}}{\Delta f_{COI}|_{t=t_2}} + \Delta f_{COI}|_{t=t_2} \right) \quad (25)$$

where $(P_{ESS})_{no}$ is the required size of the BSS at bus n , and C_{nw} is the lowest value of the coherency index of bus n .

C. Algorithm to Employ the PCA-COI Method in a power System

The previous subsections have discussed the development of the PCA-COI method as a tool to identify buses with low contributions to f^{COI} . These subsections have also discussed the employment of the PCA-COI method to allocate and size ESSs for purposes of improving the frequency stability. In order to examine the performance of the PCA-COI, this subsection presents an algorithm to deploy the PCA-COI method in a power system. The PCA-COI method can be implemented using an algorithm illustrated in the flowchart of Fig. 1.

V. THE TEST POWER SYSTEM: BLPC POWER SYSTEM

The test system is the power system located in Barbados, and is operated by Barbados Light and Power Company (BLPC). This power system is an isolated one with 20 buses as shown in Fig. 2. The test power system has a maximum load of 210 MW, and a maximum generation of 250 MW. Furthermore, BLPC power system has solar power units with a peak generation of 20 MW. Table I lists the buses of BLPC power system, maximum generation $(P_G)_{max}$, voltage ratings V_o , active and reactive power ratings P_o and Q_o , and damping factors ξ . It should be noted that the data in Table I was provided by BLPC. The data for conventional and solar generating units, in BLPC power system, is provided in Appendix I (Table V and Table VI, respectively).

Fig. 3 shows the total active power demands (P_D) of BLPC power system during one day in February 2018, and another day in July 2018. The load demands in BLPC power system are highly affected by temperature variations between Winter and Summer seasons. Moreover, the load demands are dependent on the daily morning and evening peaks during all seasons. In addition, Fig.

Fig. 2. The single-line diagram for BLPC power system.

TABLE I
BUS DATA FOR BLPC POWER SYSTEM.

Bus	$(P_G)_{\max}$ [MW]	V_o [kV]	P_o [MW]	Q_o [MVAR]	ξ [%]
1	166.9 (Conv.)	24.9	16.0	7.5	1.23
2	2.0 (Solar)	24.9	15.0	7.0	1.58
3	0.0	24.9	18.0	10.0	1.53
4	0.0	24.9	5.5	3.0	1.65
5	1.6 (Solar)	24.9	12.5	5.0	1.61
6	10.0 (Solar)	24.9	18.0	8.0	1.55
7	0.0	24.9	10.0	7.5	1.47
8	2.0 (Solar)	24.9	8.0	4.5	1.58
9	0.0	24.9	11.5	4.5	1.53
10	73.0 (Conv.)	24.9	12.5	5.5	1.39
11	0.0	24.9	12.5	6.7	1.71
12	1.4 (Solar)	24.9	5.5	3.0	1.63
13	0.0	24.9	8.0	4.5	1.68
14	2.0 (Solar)	24.9	6.6	4.0	1.57
15	0.0	24.9	2.5	1.0	1.85
16	15.0 (Conv.)	24.9	16.4	7.0	1.40
17	0.0	24.9	12.0	6.8	1.82
18	0.0	24.9	11.0	5.0	1.80
19	1.0 (Solar)	24.9	1.5	0.5	1.59
20	0.0	24.9	13.0	8.0	1.54

The notation Conv. denotes conventional generating units.

4 shows the solar power profile for the island of Barbados for one day in February 2018, and one day in July 2018.

A. Performance Evaluation of the PCA-COI Method

The flowchart of Fig. 2 was converted into a MATLAB code that has the frequencies of all buses as its inputs, while the locations and sizes of ESSs were its outputs. The frequency at each bus in BLPC power system was collected and converted into data files, which were used as inputs to the developed MATLAB code. For each transient event, the frequency at all buses was collected over an interval of 50 seconds with a sampling time of $\Delta t = 0.01$ second. Finally, 16 transient events ($B = 16$) were selected for evaluating the performance of PCA-COI method. Due to the loading levels in BLPC power system, all transient events were selected for July load demands. The 16 transient events are listed in Table II.

It should be noted that the transmission lines, in the transient events, were selected based on load flow analyses carried out

Fig. 3. The total active power demands of BLPC power system on February 15, 2018 and July 16, 2018.

Fig. 4. The solar power profile for the island of Barbados on February 15, 2018 and July 16, 2018.

TABLE II
THE TYPE, LOCATION, AND TIME OF OCCURRENCE OF THE SELECTED TRANSIENT EVENTS IN BLPC POWER SYSTEM

Label	Transient Event	Location	Time
TE1	Loss of a TL	Bus 3 to Bus 7	9 : 30 AM
TE2	Loss of a TL	Bus 15 to Bus 17	12 : 00 PM
TE3	Loss of a TL	Bus 10 to Bus 7	5 : 00 AM
TE4	Loss of a TL	Bus 1 to Bus 2	8 : 30 PM
TE5	$P_{d3} \rightarrow 0.6P_{d3}$	Bus 3 Load Demands	7 : 00 AM
TE6	$P_{d5} \rightarrow 0.5P_{d5}$	Bus 5 Load Demands	5 : 00 AM
TE7	$P_{d8} \rightarrow 1.5P_{d8}$	Bus 8 Load Demands	4 : 30 PM
TE8	$P_{d18} \rightarrow 1.3P_{d18}$	Bus 18 Load Demands	7 : 00 PM
TE9	Loss of a Generator	Bus 1: 29.7 MW Unit	4 : 00 PM
TE10	Loss of a Generator	Bus 16: 15.0 MW Unit	8 : 30 AM
TE11	Loss of a Generator	Bus 10: 20.0 MW Unit	7 : 30 PM
TE12	Loss of a Generator	Bus 1: 12.5 MW Unit	10 : 00 PM
TE13	Loss of a DGU	Bus 6: 10.0 MW PV	11 : 00 AM
TE14	Loss of a Generator	Bus 10: 13.0 MW Unit	1 : 00 PM
TE16	Loss of a TL	Bus 1 to Bus 15	2 : 15 PM
TE15	Loss of a Generator	Bus 1: 17.5 MW	3 : 45 PM

The notation TL denotes transmission line.

just before each transient event. The results of these load flow analyses showed that each of the selected transmission lines had a high loading prior to its disconnection. In addition, the time of each transient event was selected based on levels of load demands, power generation, and solar power generation. The diversity of event times aimed to test the responses of BLPC power systems to different transient events.

The BLPC power system was modeled using CYME-DIST software, with all data for generation units, loads, transmission lines, and solar generating units. The constructed model was analyzed using the *Transient Stability Package* of CYME-DIST, for all selected transient events. During each transient event, the

Fig. 5. The system frequency f collected for each of the selected transient events (listed in Table II) in BLPC power system.

frequency at all buses was collected, and converted to a data file that was used as an input to the developed MATLAB code of the PCA-COI method. The MATLAB code returned buses for connecting ESSs as well as the power ratings for each of the required ESS for each bus. Fig. 5 shows the system frequency collected for each of the 13 transient events.

The data collected from the selected transient events was used to determine the coherency index for each bus due to each transient event [1]. The matrix \mathbf{C} and its processed version \mathbf{C}^u were constructed using the data collected from the 16 transient events (see Appendix II). The application of the PCA on \mathbf{C}^u produced the matrix \mathbf{P} , which had its first row shown in Fig. 6. It could be seen from Fig. 6 that bus 5, bus 6, bus 7, bus 8, bus

13, bus 14, bus 17, and bus 18 had negative variations in their coherency indexes. These negative values suggested consistent negative coherency indexes of each of these buses. As a result, bus 5, bus 6, bus 7, bus 8, bus 13, bus 14, bus 17, and bus 18 were identified as locations for ESSs.

The identification of bus 5, bus 6, bus 7, bus 8, bus 13, bus 14, bus 17, and bus 18, as locations for ESSs allowed the determination of adequate sizes for ESSs to be connected at these buses. In this work, battery storage systems (BSSs) were used as desired ESSs. Equation (25) was used to calculate the value of $(P_{ESS})_{no}$ for each of the identified buses. Table III lists the data needed to calculate $(P_{ESS})_{no}$ for bus 5, bus 6, bus 7, bus 8, bus 12, bus 13, bus 14, bus 17, and bus 18.

Fig. 6. The principal component for the 20 buses in BLPC power system due to the selected transient events.

TABLE III

THE DATA AND TRANSIENT EVENTS USED TO CALCULATE $(P_{ESS})_{no}$ FOR BUS 5, BUS 6, BUS 7, BUS 8, BUS 13, BUS 14, BUS 17, AND BUS 18.

Bus	TE	\mathcal{C}_{nw}	$\Delta f_{COI} _{t=t_2}$	α	$(P_{ESS})_{no}$
Bus 5	TE4	-0.5219	0.0675 Hz	3.3779	5.25 MW
Bus 6	TE13	-0.4397	0.0985 Hz	6.8314	8.90 MW
Bus 7	TE10	-0.5756	0.0785 Hz	3.9444	4.25 MW
Bus 8	TE3	-0.5223	0.0288 Hz	2.3314	5.45 MW
Bus 13	TE9	-0.2515	0.0513 Hz	4.7878	3.15 MW
Bus 14	TE11	-0.4906	0.0611 Hz	2.9298	2.45 MW
Bus 17	TE7	-0.4621	0.0652 Hz	3.5989	5.55 MW
Bus 18	TE12	-0.2496	0.0527 Hz	4.3706	4.10 MW

Calculated values of $(P_{ESS})_{no}$ were rounded to the nearest 0.05.

The values of $(P_{ESS})_{no}$; $n = 5, 6, 7, 8, 13, 14, 17, 18$ were used

to select 8 BSSs, which were connected to bus 5, bus 6, bus 7, bus 8, bus 13, bus 14, bus 15, bus 17, and bus 18. It should be noted that the determined values for $(P_{\text{ESS}})_{5o}$, $(P_{\text{ESS}})_{6o}$, $(P_{\text{ESS}})_{8o}$, and $(P_{\text{ESS}})_{14o}$ did not include BSSs required by their solar generating units. Calculated sizes for BSSs at bus 5, bus 6, bus 8, and bus 14, were modified by adding BSS sizes required by solar generating units at these buses. The required BSS size at any bus with solar generating units were calculated as [31], [32]:

$$(P_{\text{ESS}}(PV))_n = \frac{P_{nR}(PV)}{2} \quad (26)$$

where $(P_{\text{ESS}}(PV))_n$ is the size of the BSS required by the solar generating units at bus n , and $P_{nR}(PV)$ is the rated power of the solar generating units at bus n . Using equation (26), the values of $(P_{\text{ESS}})_{5o}$, $(P_{\text{ESS}})_{6o}$, $(P_{\text{ESS}})_{8o}$, and $(P_{\text{ESS}})_{14o}$ (in Table III) were modified as:

$$(P_{\text{ESS}}^a)_{5o} = (P_{\text{ESS}})_{5o} + \frac{P_{5R}(PV)}{2} = 5.25 + \frac{1.6}{2} = 6.05 \text{ MW} \quad (27)$$

$$(P_{\text{ESS}}^a)_{6o} = (P_{\text{ESS}})_{6o} + \frac{P_{6R}(PV)}{2} = 8.90 + \frac{10}{2} = 13.90 \text{ MW} \quad (28)$$

$$(P_{\text{ESS}}^a)_{8o} = (P_{\text{ESS}})_{8o} + \frac{P_{8R}(PV)}{2} = 4.45 + \frac{2}{2} = 5.45 \text{ MW} \quad (29)$$

$$(P_{\text{ESS}}^a)_{14o} = (P_{\text{ESS}})_{14o} + \frac{P_{14R}(PV)}{2} = 2.45 + \frac{2}{2} = 3.45 \text{ MW} \quad (30)$$

where $(P_{\text{ESS}}^a)_{no}$ is the total BSS size for a bus with solar generating units.

In order to specify the energy storage ratings $((E_{\text{ESS}})_{no})$ for the selected BSSs, the E/P ratio was used as [16]:

$$E/P = \frac{(E_{\text{ESS}}^a)_{no}}{(P_{\text{ESS}}^a)_{no}} \quad (31)$$

The values of E/P for the selected BSSs were selected based on the discussions in references [34]. The energy storage ratings for the selected BSSs, along with E/P ratios, are provided in Table IV.

TABLE IV

THE ENERGY STORAGE RATINGS $((E_{\text{ESS}})_{no})$ FOR BSSs AT BUS 5, BUS 6, BUS 7, BUS 8, BUS 13, BUS 14, BUS 17, AND BUS 18.

Bus	$(P_{\text{ESS}})_{no}$	E/P	$(E_{\text{ESS}})_{no}$
Bus 5	6.05 MW	0.95	5.75 MW.h
Bus 6	13.90 MW	1.25	17.40 MW.h
Bus 7	4.25 MW	1.35	5.70 MW.h
Bus 8	5.45 MW	1.00	5.45 MW.h
Bus 13	3.15 MW	1.25	3.90 MW.h
Bus 14	3.45 MW	0.90	3.10 MW.h
Bus 17	5.55 MW	1.15	6.40 MW.h
Bus 18	4.10 MW	1.05	4.30 MW.h

Calculated values of $(E_{\text{ESS}})_{no}$ were rounded to the nearest 0.05.

For purposes of demonstrating the effectiveness of the locations and sizes of BSSs (selected using the PCA-COI method), BLPC power system was analyzed for some transient events as shown in Fig. 7. The results in Fig. 7 show that selected locations

Fig. 7. The system frequency collected for some transient events with and without the selected BSSs at bus 5, bus 6, bus 7, bus 8, bus 13, bus 14, bus 15, bus 17, and bus 18 in BLPC power system.

and sizes of BSSs were effective in improving the frequency stability of BLPC power system during and post transient events. These results demonstrated that charging and discharging actions of the selected BSSs were critical in restoring the frequency post transient events. During the transient stability simulations of BLPC power system (using CYME-DIST software), all selected BSSs were operated by droop controllers. The CYME-DIST software had built-in droop controllers for BSSs, and they were tuned based on reference [33]. Finally, additional test transient events are provided in Appendix III to further evaluate the performance of the PCA-COI method.

The proposed PCA-COI method has demonstrated encouraging results in terms of selecting locations and sizes of BSSs to

improve the frequency stability. Frequency responses of the test power system have shown a good ability to quickly regain steady-state conditions post transient events. Such an ability can be beneficial in minimizing interruptions in the power delivered to loads caused by actions of frequency relays in response to transient events. Test results support the employment of the PCA-COI method for selecting locations and sizes for BSSs in power systems.

VI. CONCLUSION

This paper has presented the development and performance testing of a new method to select locations and sizes of ESSs for power system applications. The developed method, called the PCA-COI method, is based on identifying buses with consistent low contributions to the center-of-inertia (COI) frequency. The low contribution to COI frequency is quantified using the coherency index, which can be calculated due to transient events. The application of the principal component analysis (PCA) allows clustering power system buses based on the variations in their coherency indexes. Buses with consistent low coherency indexes are selected as locations for ESSs. In addition, the lowest values of coherency indexes are used to determine adequate sizes for ESSs to be connected at buses with consistent low coherency indexes. The PCA-COI method is implemented and tested for BLPC power system under various transient events. Test results have shown significant improvements in the ability of BLPC power system to quickly regain steady-state conditions post transient events. The improvements in frequency stability have been found independent from the loading level, type of transient event, and level of distributed power generation. Performance results provide evidence for the efficacy and applicability of the PCA-COI method to select locations and sizes for ESSs in power systems to improve the frequency stability.

APPENDIX I

DATA FOR CONVENTIONAL AND SOLAR GENERATING UNITS

The data for all generating units (conventional and solar) in BLPC power system is provided in Table V and Table VI.

APPENDIX II

COHERENCY INDEX MATRIX FOR THE SELECTED TRANSIENT EVENTS

The coherency index matrix \mathbf{C} and its processed version, \mathbf{C}^u , are provided in equations (32) and (33) (see next page). These matrices are determined for the selected transient events in Table II. Finally, \mathbf{C} and \mathbf{C}^u are provided in their transposed formats to fit the page margins.

APPENDIX III

ADDITIONAL TRANSIENT EVENTS

This appendix provides the system frequency additional test cases that have been created in BLPC power system. These test cases are presented with and without the BSSs at bus 5, bus 6, bus 7, bus 8, bus 13, bus 14, bus 15, bus 17, and bus 18. The test

TABLE V

DATA FOR CONVENTIONAL GENERATING UNITS IN BLPC POWER SYSTEM

Label	Bus	$(P_g)_{\max}$ [MW]	Type	H [sec]	Droop
CG01	1	1.5	CoGen	1.20	N/A
CG02	1	2.5	CoGen	1.20	N/A
D10	1	12.5	LSD	2.90	4%
D11	1	12.5	LSD	2.90	4%
D12	1	12.5	LSD	2.90	4%
D13	1	12.5	LSD	2.90	4%
D14	1	29.7	LSD	4.74	5%
D15	1	29.7	LSD	4.74	5%
GT01	1	17.5	SCGT	3.65	5%
S1	1	20.0	Steam	3.65	6%
S2	1	20.0	Steam	3.65	6%
GT03	10	13.0	SCGT	2.90	9%
GT04	10	20.0	SCGT	4.74	9%
GT05	10	20.0	SCGT	4.74	9%
GT06	10	20.0	SCGT	4.74	9%
GT02	16	15.0	SCGT	2.90	9%

where LSD denotes low speed Diesel, and SCGT denotes simple cycle gas turbine.

TABLE VI

DATA FOR SOLAR GENERATING UNITS IN BLPC POWER SYSTEM

Label	Bus	$(P_g)_{\max}$ [MW]	Type	Controller
PV2	2	2.0	Distributed	Max. P_g
PV5	5	1.6	Distributed	Max. P_g
PV6	6	10.0	Central	$V_i - P_g$
PV8	8	2.0	Distributed	Max. P_g
PV12	12	1.4	Distributed	Max. P_g
PV14	14	2.0	Distributed	Max. P_g
PV19	19	1.0	Distributed	Max. P_g

cases in this appendix have been created during the peak-demand times (see Fig. 2). Table VII lists the test cases in this appendix.

TABLE VII

THE TYPE, LOCATION, AND TIME OF OCCURRENCE OF THE ADDITIONAL TRANSIENT EVENTS IN BLPC POWER SYSTEM

Label	Transient Event	Location	Time
TSC1	Loss of a Generator	Bus 10: 20.0 MW Unit	12 : 45 PM
TSC2	Loss of a Load	Bus 11: 12.5+j6.7 MVA	3 : 15 PM
TSC3	Loss of a TL	Bus 15 to Bus 17	1 : 30 PM
TSC4	Loss of a a Generator	Bus 10: 13 MW Unit	4 : 00 PM
TSC5	$P_{d17} \rightarrow 0.25P_{d17}$	Bus 17 Load Demands	2 : 15 PM

The notation TL denotes transmission line.

The system frequency f was collected (using the transient stability package of CYME-DIST software) for the 5 test cases listed in Table VII. Fig. 8 shows the collected frequency in BLPC power for the 5 test cases with and without the BSSs at bus 5, bus 6, bus 7, bus 8, bus 13, bus 14, bus 15, bus 17, and bus 18.

One can see from Fig. 8 that the selected locations and sizes of BSSs (using the proposed PCA-COI method) were effective in damping the oscillations in system frequency during and post transient events. These capabilities of the selected BSSs showed minor dependence on the type and/or location of transient events. Finally, the results of the 5 test cases demonstrated a good agreement with the test results in Fig. 7. Both sets of results confirmed the accuracy and effectiveness of selecting the locations and sizes of BSSs using the PCA-COI method.

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$$\mathbf{c}^T = \begin{bmatrix} 0.75 & 0.82 & 0.59 & 0.68 & 0.77 & 0.70 & 0.71 & 0.73 & 0.79 & 0.76 & 0.56 & 0.72 & 0.74 & 0.77 & 0.72 & 0.73 \\ 0.19 & 0.22 & 0.12 & 0.16 & 0.59 & 0.53 & 0.52 & 0.54 & 0.23 & 0.55 & 0.06 & 0.45 & 0.56 & 0.33 & 0.45 & 0.29 \\ 0.22 & 0.26 & 0.14 & 0.19 & 0.59 & 0.53 & 0.52 & 0.54 & 0.23 & 0.55 & 0.06 & 0.45 & 0.56 & 0.48 & 0.24 & 0.10 \\ 0.14 & 0.21 & 0.04 & 0.09 & 0.48 & 0.44 & 0.41 & 0.40 & 0.08 & 0.48 & -0.11 & 0.38 & 0.46 & 0.39 & 0.30 & 0.33 \\ -0.15 & -0.22 & -0.05 & -0.11 & -0.52 & -0.48 & -0.45 & -0.43 & -0.09 & -0.52 & -0.11 & -0.41 & -0.50 & -0.44 & 0.37 & -0.24 \\ -0.14 & -0.17 & -0.09 & -0.12 & -0.44 & -0.40 & -0.39 & -0.40 & -0.17 & -0.41 & -0.04 & -0.34 & -0.42 & -0.40 & -0.44 & -0.49 \\ -0.29 & 0.00 & -0.48 & -0.38 & -0.19 & -0.51 & 0.10 & -0.29 & 0.09 & -0.58 & 0.17 & 0.18 & 0.00 & 0.12 & 0.10 & 0.18 \\ -0.14 & -0.17 & -0.09 & -0.12 & -0.44 & -0.40 & -0.39 & -0.40 & -0.17 & -0.41 & -0.04 & -0.34 & -0.42 & -0.36 & -0.41 & -0.44 \\ 0.19 & 0.22 & 0.12 & 0.16 & 0.50 & 0.45 & 0.44 & 0.45 & 0.20 & 0.46 & 0.05 & 0.38 & 0.47 & 0.44 & 0.22 & 0.46 \\ 0.44 & 0.51 & 0.28 & 0.37 & 0.73 & 0.66 & 0.65 & 0.67 & 0.69 & 0.69 & 0.23 & 0.64 & 0.68 & 0.59 & 0.55 & 0.62 \\ 0.16 & 0.19 & 0.10 & 0.13 & 0.49 & 0.44 & 0.44 & 0.45 & 0.19 & 0.46 & 0.05 & 0.38 & 0.47 & 0.44 & 0.48 & 0.40 \\ 0.11 & 0.13 & 0.07 & 0.09 & 0.34 & 0.31 & 0.30 & 0.31 & 0.13 & 0.32 & 0.03 & 0.26 & 0.32 & 0.32 & 0.28 & 0.37 \\ -0.15 & -0.22 & -0.05 & -0.11 & -0.15 & -0.25 & -0.24 & -0.24 & -0.09 & -0.25 & -0.11 & -0.14 & -0.15 & -0.16 & -0.18 & -0.20 \\ -0.14 & -0.20 & -0.04 & -0.10 & -0.49 & -0.14 & -0.14 & -0.14 & -0.09 & -0.25 & -0.11 & 0.04 & 0.05 & -0.21 & -0.17 & -0.11 \\ 0.00 & 0.14 & 0.00 & -0.25 & -0.34 & 0.00 & -0.26 & 0.19 & -0.31 & -0.47 & 0.09 & 0.20 & -0.28 & -0.24 & -0.24 & -0.21 \\ 0.33 & 0.38 & 0.21 & 0.27 & 0.73 & 0.66 & 0.65 & 0.67 & 0.62 & 0.68 & 0.22 & 0.63 & 0.67 & 0.64 & 0.66 & 0.61 \\ -0.24 & -0.17 & -0.39 & 0.00 & -0.01 & -0.01 & 0.32 & 0.01 & -0.39 & -0.46 & 0.10 & -0.11 & -0.11 & -0.17 & -0.22 & -18.00 \\ -0.15 & -0.22 & -0.05 & -0.11 & -0.05 & -0.15 & -0.14 & 0.00 & -0.09 & -0.15 & -0.11 & -0.14 & -0.25 & -0.22 & -0.20 & -0.18 \\ 0.13 & 0.15 & 0.08 & 0.11 & 0.40 & 0.36 & 0.35 & 0.36 & 0.16 & 0.37 & 0.04 & 0.30 & 0.37 & 0.33 & 0.31 & 0.29 \\ 0.09 & 0.11 & 0.06 & 0.08 & 0.28 & 0.26 & 0.25 & 0.26 & 0.11 & 0.26 & 0.03 & 0.22 & 0.27 & 0.21 & 0.28 & 0.19 \end{bmatrix} \quad (32)$$

$$(\mathbf{c}^u)^T = 10^{-2} \begin{bmatrix} 0.2 & 0.7 & -0.9 & -0.3 & 0.4 & -0.1 & -0.1 & 0.1 & 0.5 & 0.3 & -1.1 & 0.0 & 0.2 & 0.3 & 0.0 & 0.1 \\ -3.0 & -2.5 & -4.3 & -3.6 & 4.0 & 3.0 & 2.9 & 3.1 & -2.3 & 3.3 & -5.5 & 1.6 & 3.5 & -0.5 & 1.7 & -1.3 \\ -2.4 & -1.8 & -4.0 & -3.1 & 4.4 & 3.3 & 3.2 & 3.4 & -2.3 & 3.7 & -5.5 & 1.8 & 3.8 & 2.4 & -2.1 & -4.8 \\ -2.6 & -1.4 & -4.4 & -3.6 & 3.7 & 2.9 & 2.4 & 2.2 & -3.6 & 3.6 & -7.1 & 1.8 & 3.3 & 1.9 & 0.3 & 0.9 \\ 3.0 & 1.3 & 5.4 & 4.0 & -6.1 & -5.0 & -4.2 & -3.9 & 4.4 & -5.9 & 3.8 & -3.4 & -5.5 & -4.1 & 15.5 & 0.7 \\ 2.4 & 2.1 & 3.2 & 2.8 & -2.0 & -1.4 & -1.3 & -1.5 & 1.9 & -1.6 & 3.9 & -0.5 & -1.7 & -1.4 & -2.1 & -2.8 \\ -4.9 & 3.0 & -10.1 & -7.3 & -2.1 & -10.8 & 5.7 & -4.8 & 5.4 & -12.6 & 7.7 & 7.9 & 3.0 & 6.2 & 5.8 & 7.8 \\ 2.2 & 1.9 & 2.9 & 2.5 & -2.1 & -1.4 & -1.4 & -1.5 & 1.8 & -1.6 & 3.6 & -0.6 & -1.7 & -0.8 & -1.6 & -2.1 \\ -2.1 & -1.7 & -3.2 & -2.6 & 2.6 & 1.9 & 1.8 & 2.0 & -2.0 & 2.1 & -4.3 & 0.9 & 2.2 & 1.8 & -1.6 & 2.1 \\ -1.8 & -0.8 & -4.4 & -3.0 & 2.6 & 1.5 & 1.4 & 1.7 & 2.0 & 1.9 & -5.2 & 1.2 & 1.8 & 0.4 & -0.2 & 0.9 \\ -2.7 & -2.3 & -3.6 & -3.1 & 2.6 & 1.8 & 1.7 & 1.9 & -2.1 & 2.1 & -4.5 & 0.8 & 2.2 & 1.8 & 2.4 & 1.1 \\ -1.3 & -1.2 & -1.8 & -1.6 & 1.2 & 0.9 & 0.8 & 0.9 & -1.1 & 1.0 & -2.2 & 0.3 & 1.0 & 1.0 & 0.5 & 1.5 \\ 0.1 & -0.3 & 0.7 & 0.4 & 0.1 & -0.5 & -0.5 & -0.5 & -0.5 & 0.5 & -0.5 & 0.3 & 0.2 & 0.1 & 0.1 & -0.1 \\ 0.0 & -0.8 & 1.2 & 0.5 & -4.3 & -0.1 & 0.0 & 0.0 & 0.7 & -1.3 & 0.4 & 2.2 & 2.3 & -0.9 & -0.4 & 0.4 \\ 2.6 & 5.4 & 2.5 & -2.6 & -4.5 & 2.6 & -2.8 & 6.5 & -3.8 & -7.3 & 4.4 & 6.8 & -3.2 & -2.4 & -2.4 & -1.8 \\ -3.9 & -3.0 & -6.1 & -4.9 & 3.6 & 2.3 & 2.1 & 2.4 & 1.4 & 2.7 & -5.9 & 1.7 & 2.3 & 1.9 & 2.2 & 1.3 \\ -2.2 & -0.9 & -5.3 & 2.6 & 2.4 & 2.3 & 9.0 & 2.7 & -5.2 & -6.7 & 4.4 & 0.3 & 0.3 & -0.9 & -1.9 & -1.1 \\ -0.1 & -0.5 & 0.6 & 0.2 & 0.6 & -0.1 & 0.0 & 1.0 & 0.3 & -0.1 & 0.2 & 0.0 & -0.8 & -0.6 & -0.4 & -0.3 \\ -1.6 & -1.3 & -2.1 & -1.8 & 1.7 & 1.2 & 1.2 & 1.3 & -1.2 & 1.4 & -2.7 & 0.6 & 1.4 & 0.9 & 0.7 & 0.4 \\ -0.8 & -0.7 & -1.1 & -1.0 & 0.9 & 0.6 & 0.6 & 0.7 & -0.6 & 0.7 & -1.4 & 0.3 & 0.7 & 0.2 & 0.9 & 0.0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (33)$$

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Fig. 8. The system frequency collected for the test transient events listed in Table VII with and without the BSSs selected for bus 5, bus 6, bus 7, bus 8, bus 13, bus 14, bus 15, bus 17, and bus 18 in BLPC power system.

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